

Facebook codebook

Academic explanatory journalism and emerging COVID-19 science

Michelle Riedlinger, Digital Media Research Centre, Queensland University of Technology
Alice Fleerackers, Interdisciplinary Studies, Simon Fraser University
December 6, 2022

Clickable Table of Contents

1. [Overview of Protocols, Instrument, and Sample for Content Analysis](#)
2. [Instructions for Content Analysis](#)
3. [Categories and codes](#)
 - a. [Facebook Public Space Type](#)
 - b. [Facebook Public Space Actor Group](#)
4. [References](#)

1. Overview of Protocols, Instrument, and Sample for Content Analysis

Coding protocols

Our sample consists of Facebook posts mentioning or linking to *The Conversation* stories that include a hyperlink to COVID-19 research published as a preprint posted to medRxiv or bioRxiv between 1 January and 30 April 2020. The final dataset contained 315 Facebook posts including a hyperlink to one of 41 stories from *The Conversation*.

Universe: All public Facebook spaces (Groups, Pages, Public Profiles) with posts made between 1 January 2020 and 26 January 2021, which mentioned or linked to one of the 41 stories in *The Conversation*.

Units of analysis: Individual public Facebook post and the public Facebook space where it was shared.

Two coders used a detailed coding instrument (see the “Coding Instructions” and Coding Categories”) and coding tool to classify each Facebook account (group, page or public profile) according to three categories: Facebook Public Space type and Facebook Public Space Actor Group. Table 1 presents an overview of the four categories and their related codes.

Table 1. Category definitions and code classification for Facebook public spaces.

	Facebook Public Space Type	Facebook Public Space Actor Group
Previous research	Pew Research Center (2020)	Adapted from Facebook research - Dutceac Segesten & Bossetta (2017) and Gerhards & Schäfer (2010, p. 149)
Relevant codes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Page ● Group ● Public Profile ● Unknown 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Political Actors ● Private Corporations ● Healthcare ● Civil Society Organisations ● Media and Communicators ● Academia ● Citizen ● Unknown (can't tell)

-
- | | |
|--|---|
| | <ul style="list-style-type: none">• None are a great fit or “Other” |
|--|---|
-

Coding users with multiple identities

All codes were mutually exclusive. However, some Facebook space bios included descriptions that suggested they belonged to more than one Actor Group (e.g. the user could be a health professional and an academic). To code these cases, the following logic was followed:

If one of the possible Actor Groups was “Academia,” the FB space was coded as Academia. This coding strategy enabled us to examine the extent to which research articles and media stories about research engage audiences beyond the academic sphere.

For all other cases, the identity described first in a user’s bio was coded as their dominant Actor Group (cf. Vainio & Holmberg, 2017). As Vainio and Holmberg (2017) argue, “what users describe themselves first with is the most relevant aspect for themselves.”

Use of outside sources

Following Tsou et al. (2015), coders were allowed to reference outside sources (e.g. Google, LinkedIn) in cases where a user’s Account Type or Actor Group was unclear from their bio information. In such cases, coders were also encouraged to consider recent posting activity by the user.

In addition, coders categorised the contents of the posts themselves along two dimensions: 1) the *purpose* of the post and 2) the use of *evidence* in the post. Table 2 provides a summary of these two categories and their related codes.

Method of data collection

Using a method adapted from Bruns et al., (2020), we accessed the data through Facebook’s metrics platform CrowdTangle, which covers public pages, public groups and public profiles on the platform only. CrowdTangle was designed for commercial social media analytics users as a third-party audience analytics tool. It was acquired by Facebook in 2016 (Newton, 2016) and is used mainly by Facebook’s commercial partners. More recently, CrowdTangle has increasingly been made available to leading scholarly social media research centres and institutes around the world. At this stage, although there is an open application form for prospective academic users, scholarly access to CrowdTangle is still provided mainly by invitation.

Using the API developed for the CrowdTangle QUT Facebook dashboard, we searched the Crowdtangle database for publicly-accessible Facebook posts that contained the URLs to research articles, preprint articles and media stories. The limitation of data collection to publicly-accessible posts is appropriate as it protects the privacy of Facebook users, but we note that this means that we are unable to trace the posting of research and media links through closed groups, private or semi-private personal profiles (e.g. profiles whose posts are available only to friends or friends of friends) or direct messaging; our analysis here is limited to the fully public spaces on the wider Facebook platform. For the purposes of this study, however, this is appropriate and sufficient: we are interested here predominantly in the major flows of research publications and media articles, which are likely to run swiftly in widely visible public spaces.

2. Coding Instructions

- 1) Use the online coding tool at: <https://www.cognitofirms.com/>
 - a) Log in with username and password.
- 2) Once you are logged in, you will find an interactive spreadsheet under the tab “Entries”
 - a) Each row represents one Facebook post to be coded.
 - b) Each column contains information related to the Facebook post to be coded:
 - i) **Status:**
 - (1) **Submitted** – When someone submits an entry, the entry status changes to “Submitted”.
 - (2) **Reviewed** – Once you view an entry on the Entries page, the entry status automatically changes to “Reviewed”.
 - (3) **Complete** – After you are finished reviewing an entry, you can set the status to “Complete” (top right hand dropdown menu) “Complete” indicates if you have finished coding this Facebook post.
 - (4) **Incomplete** – Before submission, entries saved via “Save & Resume” have a status of “Incomplete”. You can change entries back to Incomplete at any time; however, if you choose to change the entry status from Incomplete, you will need to resubmit the entry.
 - ii) **Facebook Account URL:** Displays the URL for the Facebook space (Group, Page or Public Profile).
 - iii) **Facebook Account Name:** Displays the space’s name (as declared by the administrator/s).

- iv) **Created:** Displays the date and time the Facebook post was created.
 - v) **Facebook Post Text:** Displays the text of the Facebook post.
- 3) Read the TC article that Facebook users are sharing before you start coding. This will ensure that you have the gist of the article claims and can determine if a Facebook user is agreeing or disagreeing with these claims.
- 4) To code an entry:
 - a) Select an individual entry to expand the entry details.
 - b) Click the **Edit** button on the bottom right.
 - c) Make any necessary changes to the form entry, and then click the **Update** button to save your changes.
 - d) **Top of each entry:** These boxes display information about the Facebook account.
 - e) **Bottom of each entry:** These boxes display the Facebook post text in our sample and related information.
 - f) **Coding:** This is where you select the codes.
- 5) Code each Facebook for the variables explained below (Facebook Account Type, Facebook User Actor Group, Facebook Message Purpose, Use of Evidence), using the information provided on the coding tool.
 - a) Click on the Facebook Account URL and go to the “About” information. Copy and paste this information into the Facebook Account Bio box.
 - b) If the Facebook page “About” information provides information, such as an outward link or an affiliation, you can use this information for Google searches to help with the coding.
 - c) You may also research any name, organisation, or other term you are not familiar with in order to help you determine the nature of the Facebook account – but **make sure you code that account based only on the information provided at the time of the Facebook post** (use the [Web Archive](#) where needed).
- 6) Please use the “notes” field to document any idiosyncratic findings that may be important to the researchers (anything that is unique or stands out to you), as well as **anything** you are unsure about.
- 7) Once all boxes have been checked, click “**Update.**” The record will be saved. Click on the next row entry to code.
- 8) If you have any questions, do not hesitate to ask Michelle (michelle.riedlinger@qut.edu.au) or Alice (afleerac@sfu.ca). It is always better to be sure!

3. Categories and codes

a. Facebook Public Space Type

Brief definition: Facebook Public Space Type refers to the entity the Facebook account belongs to.

Possible values: Page, Group, Public Profile, Unknown

▶ Page

Select “Page” if the Facebook space is set up as a Facebook page for a group, organisation, company, or other entity, but is not labelled as a “Group” on Facebook. It will contain a “Like” button.

If you are unsure if the Facebook space is a page, a group, or a public profile, select unknown.

Examples:

Account Name: <https://www.facebook.com/109587099063421>

Page Name: UIC College of Pharmacy

Page Bio: The official Facebook page of the UIC College of Pharmacy, Chicago campus.

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/109200595768753>

Page Name: The Christian Left

Page Bio: We're a nationwide ministry and a community for Christian progressives and their allies. We've been advocating for oppressed people since 2009, specifically for those Jesus called 'the least of these.' We highlight messy 'social issues'

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/339298396150282>

Page Name: Canadians for Political Accountability, Social Justice, a Green Future

Page Bio: Across Canada concerns are growing over the future of Canadian democracy, sovereignty and law. We value Social Justice, Political Accountability, Preservation of the Environment, Biological Diversity, the Future of our Children and the long term Welfare of the Planet

► Group

Select “Group” if the Facebook space is set up as a “Group” and represents more than one person, including events, associations, and organisations. [plural, human]

Many Facebook groups only exist on Facebook. In these cases, still select “Group.”

If you are unsure if the Facebook account belongs to a page, a group, or a public profile, select unknown.

Examples:

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/509393060015022>

Group Name: Flatten The Curve Texas

Group Bio: In times of crisis, Texans come together. After 911, Hurricane Harvey, the Bastrop Wild Fires, Texans overcame fear and uncertainty, and we took action. Our response to COVID-19 will be no different. Flatten The Curve Texas, affiliated with Flatten The Curve America, is a platform to organise, communicate, offer positive solutions and act. We will strive to inform, not inflame, plan, prepare, and take action. Where the government can't act quickly enough – Texas communities can. And we will. Join the movement now. Flatten the curve, Texas. #flattenthecurvetx

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/groups/3404395972909281>

Group Name: Reopen Delaware

Group Bio: This is a group for Delawareans and even out of staters who work or own property here. Our mission is to help with getting our state opened back up, to hold the officials accountable, and to keep everyone informed. If you are tired of quarantine and want to go on with your normal life, please join so we can begin the steps for our freedom!

► Public Profile

Select “Public Profile” if the Facebook space is identified as belonging to an individual. It will contain a “Follow” button.

If you are unsure if the Facebook space belongs to a page, a group, or a public profile, select unknown.

Note that some fan groups/pages can appear, at first glance, to be public profiles. Use the “About” information to identify the Group/Page Administrators.

Examples

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/113701169243632>

Profile Name: Beth Llewellyn McLaughlin

User bio: In 2018 a candidate for the Texas House, Beth now serves on the board of Tarrant Together, a grassroots voter activation effort. Opinions expressed here are Beth's, not those of any organisation with which she is affiliated. A passionate advocate for public schools and educators, social justice, fairness, campaign finance reform and a woman's right to make her own medical decisions.

Account URL: <https://www.facebook.com/122278571978>

Profile Name: Pattee Russell-Curry, MFT, BC-DMT, LPCC

User bio: Individual, couple, family, child, adolescent, adult, geriatric counseling, mediation and consultation. Hours of operation should read: Monday-Thursday 9 a.m.- 2 p.m., 5 p.m.-9 p.m.; Fridays 9 a.m.- 5 p.m.

► **Unknown**

Select "Unknown" if you are unsure if the Facebook account belongs to a page, a group, or a public profile.

b. Facebook Space Actor Group

Brief definition: Facebook Space Actor Group refers to the type of actor group the Facebook space represents.

Possible values: Political Actors, Healthcare, Private Corporations, Civil Society Organisations, Media and Communications, Healthcare, Academia, Citizens, Other, Unknown

Coding notes: Code only for the group the space most clearly represents. **If more than one distinct group is fundamentally relevant**, please add this group in the notes. **If the space is a public profile for an individual who is now retired**, select "Citizen." **If the Facebook space has no group or user bio**, but has a clear name (e.g., Stephen), code as: Type: Public Profile, Actor Group: Unknown.

► Political Actors

Brief definition: Political actors are “those individuals who aspire, through organisational and institutional means, to influence the decision-making process. They may seek to do this by attaining institutional political power, in government or constituent assemblies, through which preferred policies can be implemented” (McNair, 2003, p. 5).

Possible Facebook Account Types: Page, Group or Public Profile

Select “Political Actors” if the Facebook account belongs to **an individual member or group** of:

- Elected or appointed officials/offices (Executive, Legislative, Judiciary); **OR**
- Lobbyists; **OR**
- Political parties

These include actors on the local, provincial, state, federal, or international level, but *not* public health officials or organisations (see next actor group).

Examples

	Political Party [Group]	Lobbyist [Page]	Lobbyist [Public Profile]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/groups/107311756501	https://www.facebook.com/339298396150282	https://www.facebook.com/113701169243632
Name	KAY COUNTY REPUBLICANS - OKLAHOMA	Canadians for Political Accountability, Social Justice, a Green Future	Beth Llewellyn McLaughlin
Bio	This Group Page is for Registered Republicans Only. Statements made on this site by fellow Republicans may or may not represent the views of the Kay County Republican Party. Thank you. Chairman- Brian Hobbs V-Chairman - Terry Thompson...	Across Canada concerns are growing over the future of Canadian democracy, sovereignty and law. We value Social Justice, Political Accountability, Preservation of the Environment, Biological Diversity, the Future of our Children and the long-term Welfare of the Planet.	In 2018 a candidate for the Texas House, Beth now serves on the board of Tarrant Together, a grassroots voter activation effort. Opinions expressed here are Beth's, not those of any organisation with which she is affiliated. Additional Information A passionate advocate for public schools and

		educators, social justice, fairness, campaign finance reform and a woman's right to make her own medical decisions.
--	--	---

► **Healthcare**

Brief definition: The Healthcare actor group refers to **individuals or organisations** with a goal of maintaining, protecting, or recovering citizens’ physical, mental, or emotional well-being, especially by trained and licensed professionals and facilities.

Health "experts" can be academic researchers, medical practitioners and public health officials. Sometimes a researcher or medical practitioner might be on a public health board e.g. a World Health Organisation committee member, but only code those associated with an academic institution as “Healthcare” if their main job is as a national or provincial public health officer.

Possible Facebook Account Type: Page, Group or Public Profile

Select “Healthcare” if the Facebook account belongs to **an individual member or group** that is employed in an official capacity to promote and protect the health of citizen, including the following:

- Public health officers; **OR**
- Hospitals, medical clinics, other public health centres; **OR**
- Professional medical associations; **OR**
- Public health organisations;
- Medical practitioners (doctors, nurses, orderlies, etc); **OR**
- Licensed allied health practitioners (physiotherapists, chiropractors, etc); **OR**
- Medical students

This category includes actors working to protect or improve health at the local, regional, national, or international level. It does *not* include private corporations or unlicensed individuals promoting pharmaceutical products, “natural health” remedies, beauty/fitness routines, or other for-profit enterprises.

Examples

Professional Medical Association [Page]	Licensed Allied Health Professional [Public Profile]	Public Health Organisation [Page]
---	---	--

Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/165927790087108	https://www.facebook.com/122278571978	https://www.facebook.com/100356014703899
Name	Musculoskeletal Australia - MSK	Pattee Russell-Curry, MFT, BC-DMT, LPCC	Team HEPO Valenzuela - City Health Office
Bio	Improving the quality of life for Australians who have, or are at the risk of developing, arthritis, back pain, gout, osteoporosis and other musculoskeletal (MSK) conditions. Additional Information Musculoskeletal Australia has been supporting people with arthritis and musculoskeletal conditions for 50 years.	Individual, couple, family, child, adolescent, adult, geriatric counseling, mediation and consultation. Hours of operation should read: Monday-Thursday 9 a.m.- 2 p.m., 5 p.m.-9 p.m.; Fridays 9 a.m.- 5 p.m.	N/A

► Private Corporation

Brief definition: A private corporation is a business or organisation formed by a group of people for the ***purpose of generating profit***, and it has rights and liabilities separate from those of the individuals involved.

Possible Facebook Account Type: Page or Public Profile

Select “Private Corporation” if the Facebook account belongs to one of the following groups:

- Company; **OR**
- Conglomerate; **OR**
- Cooperative; **OR**
- Corporation; **OR**
- Holding company; **OR**
- Joint-stock; **OR**
- Partnership; **OR**
- General; **OR**
- Limited; **OR**
- Limited liability; **OR**
- Private limited; **OR**
- Sole proprietorship

Note: For scholarly publishers and journals, see “Academia.” For media or communications organisations and companies, see “Media and Communications.” For private corporations involved in the production of medical goods, such as vaccines, PPE, or testing kits, code as “Private Corporation”.

Examples

	Company [Page]	Company [Page]	Company [Page]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/AstraZeneca-932578013483593	https://www.facebook.com/JulpharPharmaceuticals	https://www.facebook.com/anandialabs
Name	Astra Zeneca	Julphar (Gulf Pharmaceutical Industries)	Anandia Labs
Bio	Biotech/Pharmaceuticals	Julphar is a leader in the production and distribution of high-quality, cost-effective pharmaceutical products in over five continents.	What a difference science can make.

► Civil Society Organisations

Brief definition: Civil Society Organisations are “**non-State, not-for-profit**, voluntary entities formed by people in the social sphere that are separate from the State and the market. CSOs represent a wide range of interests and ties. They can include community-based organisations as well as non-governmental organisations (NGOs). In the context of the UN Guiding Principles Reporting Framework, CSOs do not include business or for-profit associations” (emphasis added, Shift Project Ltd & Mazars LLP, n.d.). Civil Society Organisations do work outside of Facebook e.g. lobbying or fundraising

Possible Facebook Account Type: Page or Group

Select “Civil Society Organisations” if the Facebook account belongs to one of the following **groups**:

- Activist groups; **OR**

- Charities; **OR**
- Clubs (sports, social, etc.); **OR**
- Community organisations or foundations; **OR**
- Consumer organisations; **OR**
- Cooperatives; **OR**
- Foundations; **OR**
- Non-governmental organisations (NGOs); **OR**
- Non-profit organisations (NPOs); **OR**
- Private voluntary organisations (PVOs); **OR**
- Professional associations; **OR**
- Religious organisations; **OR**
- Social enterprises; **OR**
- Social movement organisations; **OR**
- Support groups; **OR**
- Trade unions; **OR**
- Voluntary associations

Note: This excludes scholarly societies and associations, which should be coded as “Academia.” It also excludes professional journalism, media, or communications associations, which should be coded as “Media and Communications,” as well as Medical/Health-related organisations, hospitals, and clinics, which should be coded as either “Healthcare”. Voluntary entities formed by people that only exist as a group on Facebook should be coded as “Citizen”.

Examples

	Social Movement Organisation [Page]	Social Movement Organisation [Group]	Non-Profit Organisation [Page]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/FarmersforClimateAction	https://www.facebook.com/groups/567963499923229	https://www.facebook.com/DavidSuzukiFoundation
Name	Farmers for Climate Action	Idle No More - West Coast Turtle Island	David Suzuki Foundation

Bio	Farmers for Climate Action	<p>United To Protect The Sacred Life of Turtle Island</p> <p>To build a strong, united and supportive network of Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples in purposeful, peaceful and collective action in the defence of Mother Earth</p>	<p>The David Suzuki Foundation works with government, business and individuals to conserve our environment by providing science-based research, education and policy work, and acting as a catalyst for the change that today's situation demands.</p>
------------	----------------------------	---	--

► Media and Communications

Brief definition: Media and communications actors are organisations, individuals, outlets, or tools used to disseminate information or data. This includes print media, the news media (incl. online), photography, cinema, broadcasting (radio and television), advertising, and public relations. This actor group also includes meso- and macro-level social media influencers, defined, for the purposes of this study, as individual users who share “personal, authentic, credible, and down-to-earth” content with a network of more than 10,000 followers (Harrigan et al., 2021).

Note: The term “influencer” should only be applied to individual users who would otherwise be categorised as “Citizens” (i.e. Political Actors, Public Health Officials, Doctors, or Academics should be coded as such, even if they have more than 10,000 followers).

Possible Facebook Account Types: Page or Group

Select “Media and Communications” if the Facebook account belongs to **an individual member or group** of:

- News organisations (newspapers, magazines, TV and radio, press agencies, online news media); **OR**
- Independent journalists; **OR**
- Bloggers; **OR**
- Social media influencers
- PR or press agencies; **OR**
- Marketing or advertising agencies.

Examples

	Social Media Influencer Official Fan Page [Group]	Media [Page]	Book Author [Public Profile]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/trust.biologist	https://www.facebook.com/ConversationEDU	https://www.facebook.com/414227761970986
Name	Trust me, I'm a "Biologist"	The Conversation EDU	The Book of Thieves
Bio	Now Trust me, I'm a "Biologist" has a group to our fans to communicate on any scientific topic! For Facebook page got to: https://www.facebook.com/trust.biologist	Independent expert-led news + analysis www.theconversation.com/au Sign up to our daily email newsletter: https://theconversation.com/au/newsletters/the-daily-newsletter-1	E-Books about the economic meltdown and honeybee colony collapse disorder. Non-Fiction: Allegory.

► Academia

Brief definition: Academia is the environment or community concerned with the pursuit of research, education, and scholarship (“Academia,” n.d.). Broadly speaking, academia has the goal to advance knowledge to better understand the world we live in (as opposed to pursuing economic or policy goals).

Note: Use this code for groups that include disciplinary technical language in their bio that indicate an academic interest of focus. This does not include primary schools, high schools, or public libraries. Practitioners such as doctors, dietitians, or lawyers should only be categorised as “Academia” if they are affiliated with an academic or research institution. Otherwise, select “Healthcare” (for doctors and dieticians) or “Citizens” (for other practitioners).

For research institutions that exist for economic or policy reasons, do not select “Academia,” but refer to one of the other groups in this codebook and leave a note if you are unsure about the coding. Research institutions affiliated with academic institutions should also be coded as “Academia.”

Possible Facebook Account Types: Page, Group or Public Profile

Select “Academia” if the Facebook account belongs to **an individual member or group** of:

- Scientists or researchers based at academic/research institutions; **OR**
- Librarians based at academic/research institutions; **OR**
- Academic or research institutions; **OR**
- Scholarly societies; **OR**
- Scholarly publishers; **OR**
- Scholarly journals; **OR**
- Students in university/higher education (e.g. college, undergrad, graduate).

Examples

	Academic Institution [Page]	Scientific Society [Group]	Research Institution [Page]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/137474816330115	https://www.facebook.com/490570534304779	https://www.facebook.com/199250609411
Name	The University of Queensland	Sociedad Ecuatoriana De Alergia, asma E Inmunologia (SEAAI)	Telethon Kids Institute
Bio	Welcome to The University of Queensland. CRICOS Provider Number 00025B The University of Queensland (UQ) was founded in 1909 and is one of Australia’s premier learning and research institutions.	The SEAAI was born after the union between the Ecuadorian Society of Allergy, Immunology and Related Sciences (SEAICA) and the Ecuadorian Society of Allergy and Imm Non-profit association	Non-profit medical research institute dedicated to discovering causes, cures and treatments for the illnesses & diseases that target our kids.

► Citizens

Brief definition: Citizens refer to **individuals and groups** belonging to the general public. This does not include political actors, civil society organisations, the media, or

academics. If a group does not do work (e.g. activism, fundraising or community support) outside of Facebook, then code as “Citizen”.

Possible Facebook Account Type: Groups, Pages, Public Profiles

Select “Citizens” if the Facebook space does not present themselves as affiliated with any of the aforementioned actor groups.

Examples

	Citizen [Page]	Citizen [Group]	Citizen [Public Profile]
Account URL	https://www.facebook.com/106853090673141	https://www.facebook.com/groups/1306950149513790	https://www.facebook.com/417787254978007
Name	The Vaccination Station	Lab Coat Heroes: Hope for Covid19	U.K Prepper Girl
Bio	This is a pro-vaxx page sharing information about all aspects of vaccination. Questions are welcome, but unsubstantiated claims will be treated with the scepticism they deserve. If you want to disagree, bring science and evidence.	A Group for the World to show their love for the Lab Coat Heroes Working on the pressing issue of Covid19. A place for Information, Hope, and Celebration. While our Doctors, Nurses and Health Care Workers need support too, this is specifically for those on the front lines of science to acknowledged and their work discussed. This is being done in the private and public labs across the world. Affectionately known as "beakers", they are our hope in dire times.	Hi, i am Kerry. A girl prepper, from sunny South Africa now living in Sunny Sussex, U.K. Thanks for being here ! Decided to do a page, share thoughts and ideas. Thank you for being here ! Kerry.

► Other

Select “Other” if none of the actor groups above seem appropriate for the Facebook account. Use the “Notes” column to provide a suggested category.

► Unknown

Select “Unknown” if you are unable to determine which actor group the Facebook account belongs to.

References

- Academia. (n.d.). In *Lexico Dictionaries*. Retrieved from <https://www.lexico.com/en/definition/academia>
- Dutceac Segesten, A., & Bossetta, M. (2017). A typology of political participation online: How citizens used Facebook to mobilize during the 2015 British general elections. *Information, Communication & Society*, 20(11), 1625–1643. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1252413>
- Gerhards, J., & Schäfer, M. S. (2010). Is the internet a better public sphere? Comparing old and new media in the USA and Germany. *New Media & Society*, 12(1), 1–24.
- McNair, B. (2003). *An introduction to political communication* (3rd ed.). London; New York: Routledge.
- Pew Research Center. (2020, June 24). As COVID-19 Emerged in U.S., Facebook Posts About It Appeared in a Wide Range of Public Pages, Groups. Retrieved July 23, 2019, from <https://www.journalism.org/2020/06/24/as-covid-19-emerged-in-u-s-facebook-posts-about-it-appeared-in-a-wide-range-of-public-pages-groups>
- Shift Project Ltd, & Mazars LLP. (n.d.). CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANIZATIONS (CSOS). Retrieved July 29, 2019, from UN Guiding Principles Reporting Framework website: <https://www.ungpreporting.org/glossary/civil-society-organizations-csos>